

EDUCATION AND PEDAGOGY

**BEYOND THE LIMITS OF MEANING AND MESSAGE
IN ILLUSTRATIVE WORKS OF JUNIOR HIGH
SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH THE THEME “NO DAY
WITHOUT ACHIEVEMENT”**

Pujiyanto*

Visual Communication Design, Universitas Negeri Malang, Indonesia.
Email: pujiyanto.fs@um.ac.id

ABSTRACT

Goals: This research aims to gain a deeper understanding of how Junior High School students interpret the theme “No Day Without Achievement” through their illustrative works, and how the meaning contained in the works transcends conventional boundaries in conveying the message. **Method:** This research uses a qualitative approach with a semiotic analysis and visual criticism of three winning illustrative works that represented Riau Province at a national level. The primary data were obtained from documents related to the illustrative works, including the competition guidelines and descriptions of the works. Secondary data were obtained from direct observation when the works were exhibited in Jakarta, and from interviews with members of the organizing committee from the Indonesian Talent Development Board, in relation to the activities and theme of the competition, members of the jury, regarding the ideas and quality of the works, and media and illustrator experts, about the creativity and artistic aspects of the works. The analysis was carried out using semiotic theory and visual criticism to explore and understand the design elements contained in the works, including color, image objects, typography, and layout. **Results:** The research results show that there are signs in the icons in the form of images, typography, color, and layout; the indexes in the form of student activities are visualized with bright colors strengthened by verbal messages of “achievement” arranged through a picture window layout; the symbols of the illustrative works contain the hopes and challenges that must be faced to achieve victory. The contextual interpretation of design elements includes (1) Color, which shows the gap between aspiration and reality; (2) Typography, which combines the balance of education and personal character; (3) Image, which combines local culture with Western culture; and (4) Layout, which indicates the presence of mental and social pressure.

KEY WORDS

Students, Illustrative Works, Design Elements, Icon, Index, Symbol, Contextual Interpretation.

INTRODUCTION

Every year the Indonesian Talent Development Board holds an illustration competition for Junior High School students from all over Indonesia, which starts at a local District/City level, and continues to a Provincial level and finally a National level. This kind of competition is held on a regular basis by various institutions, in particular by the Ministry of National Education. One particular branch of these competitions focuses on illustrations that take into consideration aspects of social and cultural sustainability, meaning that culture can be understood as a living entity that has a future impact. This type of competition requires the understanding, I believe correctly, that there are certain aspects that need to be understood in greater depth about the illustrative works created by Junior High School students. The illustrative works created by the students are developed through a collective knowledge of skills to communicate meaning in line with the progress in information gathering (Pinto Torres, Botero, & Julier, 2024). According to Singh (2018), illustrations play an important role as an information medium that is presented to the audience through image objects in the form of advice and suggestions that lead to a spirit of achievement.

In 2024, the branch of the competition for illustrations at Junior High School level introduced the theme "No Day Without Achievement". I examined the theme "No Day Without Achievement" contained in the document of Guidelines for the National Student Arts Festival (Indonesia. Kementerian Pendidikan Kebudayaan Riset dan Teknologi, 2024), and found that this activity was part of a process for sustainable character building which aims to encourage a spirit of tenacity, ambition, and hard work among students as a response to social pressure that tends to demand high achievement. The creation of illustrative works is a blend of aesthetic education that is aligned with everyday life as a divergent experience (Zhou et al., 2025). However, behind this spirit is a strong social pressure that can influence thought patterns and individual identity, especially in the context of formal education.

While carrying out a preliminary investigation, the researcher made a note of the important aspects that needed to be constructed in order to formulate a deeper understanding of the Junior High School students, art activities as a social expression, and the suitability of the theme proposed by the Indonesian Talent Development Board as understood by the Junior High School students, to determine whether the theme truly had the ability to inspire the students or on the

contrary caused excessive feelings of pressure and obligation, as stated by Birgili (2015), who explains that the emergence of ideas can be influenced by a theme. This point is important to consider in order to understand the extent to which the students convey this social pressure through the visual media used to express their illustrative works.

The illustrative works created by Junior High School students are often a channel of expression and communication for them to convey social values such as pressure, sacrifice, and ambition (Howard & Nielsen, 2025). The results of a literature search show that there is a psychological aspect constructed in the mind of the artist when focusing on a particular theme. Through the creative process, a mutation of behavioral patterns occurs that is influenced by the environment. Creativity is an expression of children's skills in responding to the school's socio-cultural environment or the environment where they are brought up (Gulliksen, 2018). Creativity can be exercised through visual signs with socio-cultural themes as a step of improvisation in work. Working effectively by utilizing social and cultural differences to create new ideas can improve the quality of innovation in the work (Mohanasundaram, 2018).

When carrying out creative work, there is a personal interaction in solving problems, which is supported by the socio-cultural conditions of the environment (Lin & Wu, 2016). The basic assumption, in this case, is that the illustrative works of Junior High School students exhibited in Best Western Hotel, Jakarta were motivated by the theme "No Day Without Achievement". According to Gafour and Gafour (2020), exploring an idea involves brainstorming through problem solving based on a theme. In expressing the theme in question, the children carried out a transfer of ideas from objects in the environment that were developed into the work they wished to create (Ryden & Sposato, 2020). It is quite evident that in their creative work, the children were influenced by environmental factors as well as their everyday socio-cultural conditions. This reinforced the decision to continue with the research about the illustrative works of Junior High School students that were created for the competition held by the Indonesian Talent Development Board.

Achievement in this context is an undertaking that can develop individual potential and contribute to self-development. In creating their illustrations, the children focus on what they are going to say, how they are going to look, and how they are going to behave as though they were the object (Singh, 2018). The students' illustrative works are a tool

to convey a moral, social, and cultural message that is relevant to their challenges and aspirations in modern society. The presence of intellectual cultural wealth can increase knowledge and provide emotional energy in creative art work (Adewumi, 2024). According to Ersoy and Başer (2014), creating an illustration requires a skill of imagining how to express ideas that are manifested in the form of information media. Therefore, it is important to understand the meaning contained in the works, whether it extends beyond literal boundaries and has the ability to offer a broader insight about the social pressures, identities, and expectations of the students.

In modern society, the conditions of globalization present the challenges of competitive conditions, and the expectations of the young generation continue to increase. The theme "No Day Without Achievement" generates tension between individual expectations and social reality that is filled with challenges. This triggers the need for a deeper understanding about the ways students articulate and respond to social pressure through visual media. The illustrative works of students with the theme "No Day Without Achievement", in which the key word is "Achievement", are an academic and non-academic accomplishment that is achieved through the cultivation and development of skills in an optimal way to improve the standard of living of society (Renkert et al., 2024). For students, reaching such an achievement can be regarded as a reflection of their efforts to overcome various social and mental pressures, and existing aspirations, and an indication of how they shape their identities and expectations amidst complex social and educational demands. These pressures make the students responsive in their behavior, thoughts, and emotions, due to the demand for achievement (Barseli, Ildil, & Nikmarijal, 2017).

The main questions that are addressed in this research are: (1) how are visual elements such as color, image objects, typography, and composition explored through the illustrative works created by Junior High School students in relation to their achievements, efforts, and ambitions? (2) how does the meaning contained in these works go beyond conventional boundaries in conveying the message? To find the answers to these questions, research was carried out using an approach with a semiotic analysis and a criticism of the illustrative works of students. The goal of the research is to gain a deeper understanding about how these works are able to communicate the social pressures, identities, and aspirations of the students, and how these aspects exceed literal and conventional meaning in conveying a social message.

The research aims to explore the meanings and messages contained in the illustrative works of Junior High School students with the theme "No Day Without Achievement", and to understand the extent to which these works surpass conventional boundaries in conveying social messages and identity. The research findings offer insight into the social and mental conditions, and the aspirations of the young generation, and show the importance of visual media as a channel of expression to communicate in Indonesian education in the global era.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Illustrations are visual decorations in the form of pictures, which have different interpretations for those who view them. Illustrations are a medium for conveying messages or strengthening the message of a written text. Illustrations can explain abstract information to a logical mind. Learning requires the use of instructional media in the form of books, which are supported by visual illustration images that facilitate the understanding of narratives in a text to stimulate the creativity of students. In a paper entitled *Illustration is an Effective Teaching Aid in the Process of Learning*, Lule and Aditi (2022) states that illustration images can develop students' interest in learning and increase their power of imagination, and as such, illustrations are an effective tool in the learning process.

There are a number of journal articles about the relationship between language skills and visual illustration images. One paper entitled *Using Illustration Images to Enhance Junior High School Students' Writing Skills* presents the results of research conducted at a particular state Junior High School in Indonesia about the use of the illustration image media in language learning. The use of illustration image media is more enjoyable for teachers in explaining the lesson material, and has the ability to improve students' understanding of writing skills. This has been proven through the results of research in which a pretest experiment without the use of illustration media produced a score of 57.08, and a posttest after using illustration media produced a higher score of 73.36. It can be concluded that the use of visual illustration as a learning medium can increase students' writing skills (Barbe et al., 2023).

Illustration image media can also be used as learning media in early childhood education because children require growth and development through attractive education. In order to provide children with adequate education, the teacher's

role is vital in helping students through different learning activities. The teacher's role in the learning process inside the classroom is as a mediator, facilitator, and motivator, to encourage children to take part in active learning. One way to increase students' concentration and motivation through attractive learning is to include the use of illustration image media creations. To prove this, Fajri et al. (2022) carried out research and presented the results in an academic paper entitled *The Implications of Naturalist Illustration Image Media on Early Childhood Learning Concentration and Motivation*, showing that the use of illustration image media has the ability to spark children's curiosity, increase their attention in following the lesson, and encourage learning activity.

On the subject of developing students' imagination in fine art classes, a paper by Sobirov (2022) entitled *Developing Students' Imagination Through Illustration and Illustrations in Fine Arts Classes* explains the importance of developing students' imagination with the use of illustration image media that is made into a book. A book that contains illustration images can guide children's wishes and develop questions that arise in their imagination. Students can utilize different media in art education to develop their competence through a comprehensive approach. In the field of fine art, students have a high imagination which enables them to visualize more easily a text in the form of images.

A different study was conducted by Karakaş and Karaca (2011), to show that illustration image media can be used to supplement foreign language teaching, as outlined in their paper entitled *Use and Importance of Illustration as Materials in Foreign Language Teaching*. These two researchers believe that illustration image media has a positive contribution in learning to understand a text. This media is frequently used by teachers to supplement their teaching and make it more effective because it stimulates the students' senses and makes it easier for them to remember the material taught. Nevertheless, it is important to be careful in selecting the right illustration image media and ensuring that it is attractive and has the ability to support the explanation of the learning material.

The current research is different from the previous studies mentioned above. While the research described above is on formal learning inside the classroom using illustration image media, the current study is on informal learning outside the classroom, focusing specifically on the activities of students taking part in an illustration competition

at the provincial level in Riau Province, Indonesia. In the research discussed above, the role of the students is as the subjects who enjoy the use of illustration image media, whereas in my own study, the students are the actors who create the illustration image media. In addition, there is no existing research which discusses illustration image media that is created by winners of a competition at provincial level for students of Junior High School.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research adopts a qualitative descriptive approach to semiotics and criticism, where the primary focus is understanding the meaning contained in a work of art through a deep exploration of the index of icons, symbols, and interpretations found in the illustrations. With the utilization of semiotic theory and visual art criticism, the researcher analyzes elements of design in the illustrative works with the theme "No Day Without Achievement". The research data were obtained from: (1) Primary Data in the form of documents of the three best illustrative works created by Junior High School students in Riau Province, which are kept by the Indonesian Talent Development Board, and supported by documents of competition guidelines and descriptions of the illustrative works. (2) Secondary Data or additional data, collected through observation at the time of the students' exhibition on 11 July 2024 at Best Western Hotel, Jakarta, and in-depth interviews with informants from: (a) the Ministry of National Education, namely Fonda Ambitasari (41 years), Head of National Illustration Competition Committee, 2024, and Keri Darwindo (47 years), Person in Charge of National Illustration Competition Activities, 2024; (b) Panel of Judges, namely Dadang Sudrajat (56 years), Jury Member 1, and Joni Agung Sudarmanto (35 years), Jury Member 2; (c) Media and illustrator experts, namely Agung Eko Budi Waspada (62 years), media expert from Institut Teknologi Bandung, and Ardian Syah (45 years), illustrator from DC. Comics.

The data collection was carried out through a number of steps, combining documentary data with data from observations and interviews. The researcher conducted a direct exploration while the exhibition was taking place to observe the contexts and interactions around the works exhibited. A visual documentation was carried out by photographing the works for further analysis. In-depth interviews were held with the three students who had created the works of art, to discover the meanings, inspiration, and creative processes behind the illustrative works. Additional interviews were held with two committee

members, two jury members, and two experts in media and illustration to understand the reasons for determining the best works and to gain a professional perspective on the theme and quality of the illustrations. The collection of supporting documents, such as the competition guidelines, description of the competition theme, and criteria for judging were used to strengthen the contexts of analysis.

The data analysis included two main steps. The first step applied Charles Sanders Peirce's Semiotic Analysis based on the typology of signs (Peirce, 2005). The researcher used a semiotic theory based on the typology of signs to identify the icons, indexes, and symbols (Sakinah, Alfiqri, & Hanifah, 2020) and Nabila and Nur Sakinah (2022) contained in each visual element of the illustrative works, including color, image object, typography, and composition. In the second step, the researcher connected the elements with the theme "No Day Without Achievement" to understand the messages that the students wished to convey, using Feldman's Visual Art Criticism at the stage of interpretation to find the expressive quality of the works (Subramaniam, Hanafi, & Putih, 2016). A criticism was carried out through a contextual interpretation to interpret the meaning in relation to the theme and symbols in

the illustrative works. Interpretation can be defined as an analysis based on the exegesis of meaning in a work (Maulana, Makawi, & Yunus, 2024).

Nofiyanti and Efi (2022) state that visual art criticism as a contextual interpretation is a presentation of criticism which is done to describe verbal values in accordance with experience in order to formulate a conclusion. The purpose of contextual interpretation is to appreciate the exegesis of an illustrative work (Bisschop, 2020) based on its design elements, and in this case the researcher analyzed aesthetic aspects based on the arrangement of composition through the layout. The visual art criticism helped the researcher to evaluate the artistic quality of the illustrative works created by the Junior High School students. Makawi (2022) writes that illustrative works created by Junior High School students represent the social reality faced by the students, so the framework of analysis includes the meanings of the images, the objective facts, and the declaration of intentional thoughts in interpreting a work. The researcher connected the findings of the semiotic analysis and visual art criticism with the insights from the in-depth interviews, to understand how the works reflect the collective thoughts of the students in the context of the theme. The stages of analysis were carried out as in the diagram below.

Figure 1: Process of Research Analysis.

To ensure that the data were more valid, a triangulation technique was applied to the documentary data, observation data, and interview data to analyze the illustrative works. This was done to ensure accuracy of interpretation and to reduce subjective bias. The research procedure comprised the following steps: Initial preparations were made by contacting the competition committee to obtain access and relevant data. Implementation included attending the exhibition to make observations and documentation. Interviews were conducted by holding in-depth interviews with members of the committee, jury, and media and illustrator experts. The analysis used semiotic theory and visual art criticism to analyze the works and data from the interviews. The conclusion involved summarizing the findings and compiling a research report. This research provides a response to the icons, indexes, symbols, and contextual interpretations in the illustrative works of students

in a comprehensive manner through collective thoughts in a competitive context.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The illustrations created by Junior High School students, which were discovered through the results of the competition, were exhibited on 11 July 2024 in Best Western Hotel, Jakarta. From all the illustrative works in the competition, the three winners from Riau Province were selected to be used as the subject of the research. These works were by: (1) Najwa Qitarah Siraj from Cendana Junior High School in Bengkalis Regency, with the title "Achieving Through Art, Stepping into the Future" (*"Berprestasi Melalui Seni, Menapak Masa Depan"*); (2) Faustin Mirabella Hierajaya from Mutiara Harapan Plus Junior High School in Pelalawan Regency, with the title "No Day Without Achievement" (*"Tiada Hari Tanpa Berprestasi"*); and (3) Kamilla Zahra from Jamiatul Muslimin IT

Junior High School in Dumai City, with the title “Actively Achieving and Working for the Country”

(“Aktif Berprestasi Berkarya Untuk Negara”), as shown below.

Figure 2: Illustrative Works.

According to head of committee Fonda Ambitasari (interview, 10 July 2024), the purpose of the competition was to look for talented students in the field of art and culture as a way of motivating the young generation to continue to strive for success amidst the increasingly complex demands in education and in daily life. According to Keri Darwindo (interview, 11 July 2024), who was the person in charge of competition activities, students can discover and develop their self-potential and talent by abstracting, narrating, and articulating through visual messages in an illustrative work. The illustration competition is a media for cultural preservation and development, which includes safeguarding the traditions, customs, norms, beliefs, and cultural heritage of the present generation for future generations (Zhang & Seong, 2024). Through this activity, students can explore ideas, creative experiments, and design processes to produce an illustrative work (Cezzar, 2020).

The students used unlimited creativity in their work to produce original ideas through the discovery of artistic expression in a variety of contexts (Samaniego et al., 2024). Their works focus mainly on objects in the center that are surrounded by supporting elements such as a school environment, a river, or city buildings. This composition portrays the social pressure that comes from various sides, such as the family, the community, and the educational environment. These elements show how the students exist in the midst of the social and cultural changes that they experience. The narratives of the illustrations appear to show more verbalistic aspects, which according to Dadang Sudrajat (interview, 11 July 2024) reflect the struggles that the students experience in the face of high expectations and environmental constraints. The illustrative works created by the Junior High School students are an

expression of the facilities that exist in the real world (Noel et al., 2023). The works use different color combinations to create particular moods, such as bright colors (yellow, red, orange, and purple) to portray aspirations, hopes, and optimism. Dark colors (blue, grey, and brown) as background fillers, according to Joni Agung Sudarmanto (interview, 11 July 2024), are often used to show tension, fatigue, or sadness. These colors show the conditions of the spiritual lives of the students that are visualized in the illustrative works with the theme “No Day Without Achievement”.

Keri Darwindo (interview, 11 July 2024) gave the following explanation about the three works exhibited: (1) Najwa Qitarah Siraj’s work entitled “Achieving Through Art, Stepping into the Future” describes the opportunity for higher studies that can be reached as a result of the achievements she has made. The student is making an effort to achieve so that she can gain entrance to her favorite school of choice through the achievement path. Taking part in the competition at provincial and national level is the first step towards her dream of becoming a student with high achievement in the field of the arts; (2) Faustin Mirabella Hierajaya’s work entitled “No Day Without Achievement” portrays the enthusiasm of a student who is working to make a contribution to her local area and to the nation. The young generation must preserve their culture, and one way to do this is through the illustrative work that she created as a moral message to encourage other students to take part in safeguarding their culture. (3) Kamilla Zahra’s work entitled “Actively Achieving and Working for the Country” shows the art activities of children which are recorded in her work. According to Dadang Sudrajat (interview, 11 July 2024), children are always enthusiastic to practice and work hard to reach their goals and

dreams, to achieve success, to win and to make their nation proud. If children are motivated to achieve great things they will tend to be oriented towards making the maximum effort needed to achieve success (Haru, 2023).

The three works exhibited are a representation of ideas, and a reflection of the environment of the students, who represent 25 students from Riau Province. They not only managed to translate the ideas inside their heads but continued to contemplate and modify these ideas as they were working to discover new things (Noel, 2022). According to Dadang Sudrajat (interview 11 July 2024), the illustrations produced portray the everyday lives of the students in the context of education, specifically in their school environment, expressed through their talent in the arts. Joni Agung Sudarmanto (interview 11 July 2024) explains further that the illustrative works appear to be a display of Indonesian students' imagination about their future. They also present their ethnic identity and their environment as members of a coastal community, or a community that lives close to a river, while not forgetting to present themselves as part of an ethnic community that has a strong art tradition. Some of the works are even an expression of an urban community that is portrayed through their profiles as "Barbie". Barbie is a socialite who symbolizes the dreams of the students to win a competition and set a standard of success that reflects an ideal image (Nisa & Adi, 2023). As "Barbies", says Ardian Syah (interview, 20 July 2024), the students express themselves in their illustrative works through image objects that are always spirited, full of joy, and supported by bright colors to symbolize the elation that represents independence to work within the emotions of idealistic demands as part of the future generation.

The main character is usually the student who is involved in academic activities such as learning together with friends, attending class, or taking exams. The illustrations are often supplemented with details that reflect an emotional mood, such as a serious expression when studying or an anxious facial expression. Some of the illustrative works also highlight an environmental setting such as a simple study room or a crowded classroom, to emphasize the student's social situation. According to Agung Eko Budi Waspada (interview, 18 July 2024), the illustrative works present stories about the complex balance between academic success and the social challenges faced by the students. The students create their narrative illustrations using free, spontaneous experiments that extend beyond the boundaries of scientific disciplines, showing that the students have a comprehensive

understanding of the importance of technique and artistic expression (Die & Li, 2023). Some of the narratives reflect the internal conflict of a student who is focused and studies diligently but is also seeking an aspect of achievement in the arts. Other narratives portray the social inequality that exists between ethnic conditions, with clear differences in the environments of students who have access to modern facilities and those who study within limitations.

The illustrations created by Junior High School students with the theme "No Day Without Achievement" show the high expectations of the students and the state. The theme reflects a broad range of activities, including the environment of the activities and the elements of objects that are applied to the works through the process of activities in finding solutions to problems (Neramballi, Sakao, & Gero, 2025). According to Ardian Syah (interview, 20 July 2024), the students focus on depicting thematic imagery through a visual dimension, which includes students with an ethnic background, their social conditions as students, and the image of an urban future. According to Agung Eko Budi Waspada (interview, 18 July 2024), this reflects the pressure often experienced by students to reach standards set by the environment, their strong ethnic feelings and the need to preserve their identity, the social conditions needed to pursue the future, and also the dream of reaching a future through the bright lights of the metropolis.

The choice of typography is extremely important for determining the success of the information messages conveyed by the children (Syakir et al., 2022). According to Dadang Sudrajat (interview, 11 July 2024), the typography in the work with the title "Achieving Through Art, Stepping into the Future" uses yellow Tempus Sans ITC font, reinforced with a black outline so that the words/sentence in the title are clearer and easier to read. The work with the title "No Day Without Achievement" uses orange Lucida Fax font, with a black outline around the letters to make the letters bold and strong so that they are easier and quicker to read. The work entitled "Actively Achieving and Working for the Country" uses orange Maiandra GD font, reinforced with a "burning" effect to create an impression of enthusiasm about the competition activities.

The students describe their achievements using different styles, varying from simple to complex. An example of a simple style is seen in an illustration which uses basic lines with little detail, focusing on actions such as reading or writing. According to

Ardian Syah (interview, 20 July 2024), a complex style involves the use of more detailed visual elements, such as a background with full color and symbols such as a river, a school environment, or a dazzling urban setting. The style of organizing image objects in the field is arranged based on the expression of the students, and ranges from individual academic success to a depiction of a collaboration with classmates. Achievement is often connected with artistic symbols, school activities, and ethnic environments.

Traditional icons such as a boat, a river environment, and elements of ethnic art appear in the illustrations as indexes that remind of the importance of preserving cultural roots in the midst of modernity. Promoting traditional culture helps to increase the understanding of the relational nature of collective reflection in the individual student (Pinto Torres et al., 2024). These elements are symbols of cultural identity that remain an important part of the students' life journeys. The boat, which is a type of transportation that carries passengers to a dock or another island, means that the competition is a vehicle for achieving the dream and aspiration of becoming the best, or the winner. In the interpretation of the object of the boat or sampan is a symbol of hope that the students are riding towards the future, while the school uniform is an expression of achieving success, and the bright lights of the city and symbol of Barbie represent images of Western culture, which is considered to promise success. All the elements of transmission to achieve social success in the future appear very strongly. They all represent the struggle for success, or the chain that reflects limitations. Visually, there is a tendency to position the student as the center of attention, surrounded by elements that represent external pressure, such as their ethnicity that they may be doubting, or the school uniform as another dimension that casts doubt on their future. The choice of fonts, letter colors, and the reinforcement of letters in the titles is not merely for appearance but also a way of strengthening the visual message of the picture. Yellow and orange in the title symbolize a message of spirit and enthusiasm to create an illustrative work, while the outline of the title strengthens and emphasizes the message that is conveyed through visual language. According to (Kusumawati, 2019), the titles that are reinforced with particular letter types, colors, and letter effects have three functions in communication – for naming, interaction, and transmission of information. Naming is interpreted as the identification of visual objects in the illustration images, interaction as the emotional ideas in conveying the message, and transmission of information as the conveying of the message to the audience.

The typography in the form of sentences is realized in the titles of the illustrative works that are positioned on the bottom right, top center, and bottom center of the works. The positioning of the title on the bottom right represents the place where a person signs an agreement and is responsible for the message conveyed. The message feels warm in the way it is conveyed through the title so that the audience feels respected. The title that is positioned in the center at the top of the illustration in a symmetrical manner gives a formal impression. Placing the title in this position enables the audience to capture the message first of all from the verbal title, and only then is the message reinforced by the visual image. The title that is positioned symmetrically in the center at the bottom of the illustration is intended to underline and interpret the visual message of the picture that achievement is not only for the individual but also for the country.

The students developed their ideas continuously through design principles and design experiments, and there was a need for a verbal message in order for their messages to be received by the audience (Jensen et al., 2023). In the illustrations by Faustin Mirabella Hierajaya and Kamilla Zahra, the verbal messages in the titles "No Day Without Achievement" and "Actively Achieving and Working for the Country" stand out as symbols for children of a similar age to strive for success in non-academic fields of fine art and performing art. These verbal messages are presented so that there is not a difference of opinion in the perception of the audience in the way they view the visual message, which can be interpreted as portraying a hope for the young generation to fulfill the country's programs in the future through their achievements. In the work entitled "Achieving Through Art, Stepping into the Future" by Najwa Qitarah Siraj, the message prioritizes the visual image, which dominates the entire field. The visual message stands out because the image object is the activities of playing music on the accordion and dancing the Zapin dance, which characterize the culture of Riau Province. Through this visual message, the audience captures the message first from the picture, which invites children to achieve without having to abandon their local culture.

Overall, the colors of the illustrations are dominated by purple and brown. Purple symbolizes the hope of gaining recognition, and this is reinforced by the appearance of the illustration image. Purple is interpreted as a dream becoming reality, achieving the ambition of being the best child, becoming a champion, a child who achieves success as the hope of the nation and a successor to the future

generation. Purple also interprets messages of social criticism, specifically that everything is regulated by those who hold power. If we look at this opinion, the illustrative works created are a social criticism about the students who are a tool of propaganda to promote their area by winning the illustration competition. The color brown is a symbol of maturity in taking part in the competition, which has become a regular activity for students who are skilled at drawing. Brown can be interpreted as showing maturity, reliability, pessimism in the illustration competition. Mature in action means doing something that is beneficial and has positive value for a progressive and independent Indonesia.

Looking closely at the illustrations by Najwa Qitarah Siraj, Faustin Mirabella Hierajaya, and Kamilla Zahra, it can be seen that they show the composition style icon of picture window layout, which places more importance on the visual image (Pilelienė & Grigaliūnaitė, 2016). Picture window layout is an index of illustration style that fills the area for displaying the image in the way that a person sees all the objects outside their house through a window frame. The layout style in these illustrations prioritizes the visual message (the image) rather than the verbal message (the writing). This layout is a symbol of the numerous problems that need to be conveyed to the audience so the students reflect the messages together in one field, creating an impression of crowdedness inside the single frame. This layout style can be interpreted as the large number of messages that the student wishes to present to the audience about the need for achievement in fulfilling the vision of Golden Indonesia 2045.

CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions of this research are based on the following typology of signs: (1) The icons in the form of illustrative works which expose objects of boys and girls combine primary and secondary colors and are reinforced by the messages in the titles that use Tempus Sand, Lucinda Fax, and Maiandra GD fonts. The elements of color, image, and typography are arranged in a window layout. (2) The indexes are reflected in the art activities of the Junior High School students which are supported by the verbal message of "achievement", reinforced with yellow, red, blue, orange, and purple colors and arranged in a picture window layout frame that indicates a spirit of winning. (3) The symbols in the illustrative works that visualize the students' activities combine traditional and modern elements in their contemporary works so that they can become champions who make

their families, schools, and local area happy. The illustrative works created by Junior High School students symbolize the challenges, hopes, and conditions faced by the young generation in their journey towards academic success and success in their social and cultural lives.

The findings about the illustrative works created by Junior High School students show that there is a contextual interpretation in the following design elements: (1) Color, which shows the gap between aspiration and reality. The illustrative works contain traditional colors which are the primary colors red, yellow, and blue, combined with secondary and tertiary colors such as orange and purple. The appearance of these colors is used to interpret the imbalance between the students' aspirations to succeed in the world and the social reality they face, such as education disparities, pressure to preserve tradition, and the expectations of the community where the students grow and develop. (2) Typography, which combines a balance of education and character. The titles of the illustrative works use the keyword "Achievement", in Tempus Sans ITC, Lucida Fax, and Maiandra GD fonts which are combined with yellow and orange. The students choose letter types and colors that interpret the pressure and commitment related to the expectations of themselves, their families, and their communities. Even though they may find themselves in difficult conditions, their mental and physical resistance is reflected in the face of various limitations. This indicates a close connection between the world of education and the deep character values of the students. (3) Image, which combines local culture with Western culture. The presence of local and Western cultural elements, such as an image of a traditional house together with high-rise buildings, can be interpreted as portraying the significant clash of globalization in shaping the views of the young generation about success. On the other hand, the appearance of image objects such as traditional music and modern music shows the passion that arises from ambivalence because the students must find a balance between their local identities and the appeal of global culture. (4) Layout, which points to mental and social pressure. The use of a picture window layout, which presents the objects across the entire field, bordered by a frame on each side, can be interpreted as an expression of the pressure faced by the students. This pressure is the social and economic demands they face, in reference to the prize they will get if they win the competition and the pride they will bring to their school and home area. The students use a number of ways in their struggle to meet the standards of success that they often perceive as a burden.

RECOMMENDATIONS, LIMITATIONS, AND FUTURE RESEARCH

Recommendations

Junior High School students are still growing and developing, and for this reason good learning is needed that suits their characters. Learning should focus not only on technical aspects but also on the quality of contextual argumentation, so that the students are more focused in their activities (Lee et al., 2024). Students should not be confined in their work, and more importance needs to be placed on the students' independence so that they become individuals who are not influenced by anyone in any circumstances. Students should not be subjected to pressures that arise merely as a result of the emotional demands of those in power, or stakeholders, where the outcome is not determined by the students themselves. Students need to be guided to develop a religious, nationalist, independent character, a character of mutual cooperation and high integrity to realize the golden generation of Indonesia in 2045. Research is an important insight into the future conditions of Indonesian students in articulating their challenges and hopes through fine art, specifically illustrative works, in the context of education in Indonesia in the global era. Through the results of this research, a deeper understanding can be gained about the ways education, cultural identity, and globalization interact in shaping the aspirations and challenges of the young generation at the present time.

Limitations

The students were not free to create their illustrations because they were restricted and confined by the theme "No Day Without Achievement" that they were forced to follow. In their work for the competition, the students were guided by mentors or tutors who largely intervened in the students' illustrations. In order for the illustration images to reflect the true conscience of the students, they need freedom, without a theme and without pressure from their mentor or tutor who may guide them beyond their own rational thoughts.

Future Research: This research is based on a specific theme that is presented in an illustration competition for Junior High School students in Indonesia. The results of the research can be used as a starting point that opens up possibilities for future researchers to develop and improve further. Future research may focus on the character of illustration images by school children and university students that are influenced by geographic, demographic, and psychographic elements, and their behavior.

REFERENCES

- Adewumi, K. C. (2024). Rereading art workshops as an interaction ritual for knowledge formation and artists' development. *Cogent Arts & Humanities*, 11(1), 2429929. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311983.2024.2429929>
- Barbe, K., Sakkir, G., Syafitri, E., & Dollah, S. (2023). Using Illustration Images to Enhance Junior High School Students' Writing Skills. *Journal of Language Learning and Assessment*, 1(1), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.71194/jlla.v1i1.74>
- Barseli, M., Ildil, I., & Nikmarijal, N. (2017). Konsep Stres Akademik Siswa. *Jurnal Konseling dan Pendidikan*, 5(3), 143-148. <https://doi.org/10.29210/119800>
- Birgili, B. (2015). Creative and Critical Thinking Skills in Problem-based Learning Environments [Creative and Critical Thinking Skills in Problem-based Learning Environments]. *Journal of Gifted Education and Creativity*, 2(2), 71-80. <https://doi.org/10.18200/JGEDC.2015214253>
- Bisschop, W. T. C. (2020). Interpretation and Aesthetic Appreciation. *Journal of Literary Theory*, 14(1), 1-9. <https://doi.org/10.1515/jlt-2020-0001>
- Cezzar, J. (2020). Teaching the Designer of Now: A New Basis for Graphic and Communication Design Education. *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation*, 6(2), 213-227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sheji.2020.05.002>
- Die, H., & Li, G. (2023). Fostering Creative Expression: Integrating the Artistic Form and Cultural Influence of Yichun Print in Art Education. *Arts Educa*, 36, 23-42. <https://doi.org/10.6035/artseduca.3602>
- Ersoy, E., & Başer, N. e. (2014). The Effects of Problem-based Learning Method in Higher Education on Creative Thinking. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116, 3494-3498. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.01.790>
- Fajri, Z., Toba, R., Muali, C., Ulfah, M., & Zahro, F. (2022). The Implications of Naturalist Illustration Image Media on Early Childhood Learning Concentration and Motivation. *Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 6(4), 3278-3290. <https://doi.org/10.31004/obsesi.v6i4.2092>
- Gafour, O. W. A., & Gafour, W. A. S. (2020). *Creative Thinking Skills - A Review Article*. ResearchGate GmbH. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349003763>
- Gulliksen, M. S. (2018). Norwegian parents' perspective on environmental factors that influence creativity – An empirical grounding for future studies. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 88, 85-94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijer.2018.01.013>

- Haru, E. (2023). Upaya Meningkatkan Motivasi Berprestasi Pada Mahasiswa. *Jurnal Alternatif Wacana Ilmiah Interkultural*, 12(01), 60-74. <https://doi.org/10.60130/ja.v12i01.117>
- Howard, F., & Nielsen, A. M. W. (2025). Categories and Dilemmas of Youth Arts Programmes in Denmark and England. *International Journal of Art & Design Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jade.12571>
- Indonesia. Kementerian Pendidikan Kebudayaan Riset dan Teknologi. (2024). *Pedoman Festival Lomba Seni Siswa Nasional SMP/MTS/Sederajat 2024*. Kementerian Pendidikan Kebudayaan Riset dan Teknologi - BPTI. <https://drive.google.com/file/d/11VgBKsAVaGZji2ad-ERiYFdcUVZekcs3/view>
- Jensen, J.-O., Jørgensen, H. H., Sand, A.-L., Hansen, J. H., Lieberoth, A., & Skovbjerg, H. M. (2023). Play Types, Design Principles and Participation in Play: How Is it Possible to Design for Participation in Play? *EDeR – Educational Design Research*, 7(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.15460/eder.7.1.1978>
- Karakaş, A., & Karaca, G. (2011). Use and Importance of Illustration as Materials in Foreign Language Teaching. *Balikesir University Journal of Social Sciences Institute*, 14(26), 351-357. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/272493455>
- Kusumawati, T. I. (2019). Komunikasi verbal dan nonverbal. *Al-Irsyad: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Konseling*, 6(2), 83-98. <https://doi.org/10.30829/al-irsyad.v6i2.6618>
- Lee, W., Mentzer, N., Jackson, A., Bartholomew, S., & Clevenger, A. (2024). Defining and Evaluating Argumentation Quality in the Context of Design Thinking: Using High School Students' Design Critiques from Foundational Engineering Courses. *Design and Technology Education: An International Journal*, 29(3), 11-35. <https://openjournals.ljmu.ac.uk/DesignTechnologyEducation/article/view/2530>
- Lin, C.-S., & Wu, R. Y.-W. (2016). Effects of Web-Based Creative Thinking Teaching On Students' Creativity and Learning Outcome. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 12(6), 1675-1684. <https://doi.org/10.12973/eurasia.2016.1558a>
- Lule, A., & Aditi, M. (2022). Illustration is an Effective Teaching Aid in the Process of Learning. In *Proceedings of the 7th International Conference on Innovations and Research in Technology and Engineering (ICIRTE-2022)*, organized by VPPCOE & VA, Mumbai-22, INDIA. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4113697>
- Makawi, F. E. (2022). Konseptual Framework Dalam Kritik Seni: Kolektif Interpretasi Karya Seni Rupa Kontemporer. *Jurnal Imajinasi*, 6(2), 92-102. <https://doi.org/10.26858/i.v6i2.38461>
- Maulana, F., Makawi, F. E., & Yunus, P. P. (2024). Interpretasi Karya Djoko Pekik "Berburu Celeng". *Journal of Arts Education and Design*, 1(1), 9-14. <https://doi.org/10.62330/artsedes.v1i1.47>
- Mohanasundaram, K. (2018). Curriculum Design and Development. *Journal of Applied and Advanced Research*, 3(Suppl. 1), S4-S6. <https://doi.org/10.21839/jaar.2018.v3S1.156>
- Nabila, R., & Nur Sakinah, R. M. (2022). Analysis of Icons, Indexes, and Symbols in YouTube Advertisement of SilverQueen Very Berry Yoghurt. *Journal of Scientific Research, Education, and Technology (JSRET)*, 2(1), 1-20. <https://doi.org/10.58526/jsret.v2i1.34>
- Neramballi, A., Sakao, T., & Gero, J. S. (2025). Is product-service system designing different from product designing? A cognitive study of experienced product designers. *Design Science*, 11, e8. <https://doi.org/10.1017/dsj.2025.4>
- Nisa, I. K., & Adi, I. R. (2023). The Cultural Construction of Barbie in American Discourses: Norman Fairclough's Critical Discourse Analysis. *Rubikon: Journal of Transnational American Studies*, 10(2), 144-160. <https://doi.org/10.22146/rubikon.v10i2.86576>
- Noel, L.-A. (2022). Designing New Futures for Design Education. *Design and Culture*, 14(3), 277-291. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17547075.2022.2105524>
- Noel, L.-A., Ruiz, A., van Amstel, F. M. C., Udoewa, V., Verma, N., Botchway, N. K., et al. (2023). Pluriversal Futures for Design Education. *She Ji: The Journal of Design, Economics, and Innovation*, 9(2), 179-196. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sheji.2023.04.002>
- Nofiyanti, N., & Efi, A. (2022). Kritik seni dan fungsi melakukan kritik seni. *Gorga: Jurnal Seni Rupa*, 11(2), 276-280. <https://doi.org/10.24114/gr.v11i2.34618>
- Peirce, C. S. (2005). *Semiotica*. *Perspectiva*. <https://www.scribd.com/document/738235730/Charles-Sanders-Peirce-Semiotica-1>
- Pilelienė, L., & Grigaliūnaitė, V. (2016). Effect of Visual Advertising Complexity on Consumers' Attention. *International Journal of Management, Accounting & Economics*, 3(8), 489-501. http://www.ijmae.com/files/accepted/510_final.pdf
- Pinto Torres, N., Botero, A., & Julier, G. (2024). Politicizing the Pictogram: Participatory Design Approaches within Indigenous Community Communication. *International Journal of Design*, 18(1), 77-93. <https://doi.org/10.57698/v18i1.05>
- Renkert, S., Han, J., Briller, S., Kelley, T., & Hammoud, A. (2024). Engaging ethnography in the human-centered design technology classroom. *Design and Technology Education: An International Journal*, 29(3), 36-55. <https://openjournals.ljmu.ac.uk/DesignTechnologyEducation/article/view/2420>

- Ryden, W., & Sposato, D. (2020). Cultivating Convergence through Creative Nonfiction: Identity, Development, and the Metaphor of Transfer. *Journal of Creative Writing Studies*, 5(1), 2. <https://repository.rit.edu/jcws/vol5/iss1/2>
- Sakinah, R. M. N., Alfiqri, J., & Hanifah, L. N. (2020). Analysis of icons, indexes, and symbols in YouTube advertisement of Wardah perfect bright creamy foam facial wash. *Apollo Project: Jurnal Ilmiah Program Studi Sastra Inggris*, 9(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.34010/apollo.v9i1.5332>
- Samaniego, M., Usca, N., Salguero, J., & Quevedo, W. (2024). Creative Thinking in Art and Design Education: A Systematic Review. *Education Sciences*, 14(2), 192. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14020192>
- Singh, R. K. (2018). Role of Illustration in Advertising. *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, 6(1), 454-462. <https://www.ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT1802393.pdf>
- Sobirov, S. T. (2022). Developing Students' Imagination Through Illustration and Illustrations in Fine Arts Classes. *International Journal of Social Science Research and Review*, 5(6), 12-16. <https://doi.org/10.47814/ijssrr.v5i6.408>
- Subramaniam, M., Hanafi, J., & Putih, A. T. (2016). Teaching For Art Criticism: Incorporating Feldman's Critical Analysis Learning Model In Students' Studio Practice. *Malaysian Online Journal of Educational Technology*, 4(1), 57-67. <https://mojet.net/index.php/mojet/article/view/76>
- Syakir, S., Sobandi, B., Fathurrahman, M., Isa, B., Anggraheni, D., & Verayanti, S. (2022). Tamarind (*Tamarindus indica* L.): Source of Ideas Behind the Semarang Batik Motifs to Strengthen Local Cultural Identity. *Harmonia: Journal of Arts Research and Education*, 22(1), 78-90. <https://doi.org/10.15294/harmonia.v22i1.36579>
- Zhang, W., & Seong, D. (2024). Cultivating Creativity and Engagement in Painting Education Through Ai Digital Painting: An Interdisciplinary Approach to Enhance Student Learning Experience. *Arts Educa*, 41, 166-176. <https://doi.org/10.58262/ArtsEduca.4112>
- Zhou, G., Luo, C., Yunus, M. M., & Mansor, A. Z. (2025). The Use of Triggered Teaching Behavior (TTB) to Improve Artistic Thoughts (AT) Effectiveness for Digital Media Technology Students in Mianyang Teachers' College in China. *Arts Educa*, 42, 85-102. <https://doi.org/10.58262/ArtsEduca.4206>